

Research Article

Residual Effect of Integrated Nutrient Management Approach on the Growth and Yield of Amaranthus (*Amaranthus cruentus* L.) on an Acidic Soil of Southeastern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at the experimental farm of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, to ascertain the residual effect of Integrated Nutrient Management (INM) on the growth and yield of amaranthus (*amaranthus cruentus* L) on an acidic soil of Southeastern Nigeria. The treatment comprised of sole urea (UA) applied at 6.25t/ha, sole CaCO₃ (LM) applied at 4t/ha, sole pig waste (PW) applied at 10t/ha, combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea +5t/ha of mulch (PW+UA+ML), combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea +5t/ha of mulch + 2t/ha of CaCO₃ (PW+UA+ML+LM), combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea + 5t/ha + CaCO₃ (PW+UA+ LM) and a control (C). The treatments were replicated three times in a Randomized Complete Block Design and were applied once in August 2010. The test crop amaranthus was planted in 2010 and 2011 on the same piece of land. The results obtained showed that PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased the plant height at the two years, with the values of 46 cm and 39cm respectively. It also significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased the dry matter yield, nitrogen and potassium concentration in the plants. The study showed that the combination of PW+UA+ML+LM improved most of the plant parameters tested and had a lasting residual effect in the soil.

Keywords:

Integrated Nutrient Management, Amaranthus, soil and residual effect

INTRODUCTION

Amaranthus is one of the popular leafy vegetables grown in Nigeria, which form not just part of the populace diet but is also a source of income for the farmers. As a vegetable, it provides excellent means of supplementing the mineral and vitamin deficiencies in the diets when they are properly cooked (Uwaegbute, 1989). Amaranthus produces the highest amount of proteins and dry matter per unit area and time among the vegetables (Messiaen, 1992) and therefore very valuable source of combating under nutrition and malnutrition in Nigeria (Uwaegbute, 1989). Agronomical, Amaranthus require a well drained soil rich in nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium and will perform better in non acidic conditions (Lucas and Ojeifo, 1985, Mbonu and Arifalo, 2006). However, the rapid decline in soil fertility in the Southeast Nigeria (Ogbodo and Nnabude, 2012) coupled with the acidity (Osodeke, 2000) is a major constraint to the successful production of amaranthus in the area. Organic manure, especially farm yard manure had been used extensively for the production of amaranthus (Akanbi, *et al*, 2007), but its effect when applied to the soil is not felt immediately because it slowly releases its nutrients there by favoring a long term production and demerits short term usage. Apart from being a slow release soil input, its scarcity, transportation and bulkiness are major limitations to their sole usage as a soil amendment for amaranthus production in the area. In the same vein the use of sole fertilizers had been adapted for crop production and has been reported to increase the growth of crops but the effect is short lived. Sole mineral fertilizers when applied to the soil, had been reported to reduce the colonization of plant roots with mycorrhizae and inhibit symbiotic N fixation by rhizobia due to high N fertilization (Chen, 2006). The continuous use of inorganic fertilizer alone as soil amendment aggravate soil acidity, nutrient imbalance and loss of organic matter which leads to reduced nutrient uptake (Ojeniyi and Adeniyi, 1999).

Even though the two types of soil amendments discussed above had some negative effects, their combination may be of beneficial importance in order to boost crop production. One of the ways by which they can merge to unshackle their potential is through Integrated Nutrient Management (INM). Integrated nutrient management which is part of Integrated Soil Fertility Management (ISFM) focuses on the combined use of organic and inorganic sources of plant nutrients (Vanlauwe *et al*; 2001; Chianu and Tsujii, 2005). The combined use of organic and inorganic fertilizers for crop production had been found to increase crop yield (Asadu and Unagwu, 2012) and sustain soil productivity (Ageeb *et. al*, 2000). Another benefit of their combination is that inorganic fertilizers assist in the decomposition of the organic fertilizers when they are applied together (Ojeniyi and Adegboyey, 2003, Adeniyi and Oyeniyi 2005). According to Funchs *et al*; (1970) as cited by Asadu and Unagwu (2012) nutrients from mineral fertilizers enhance

the establishment of crop while those from organic manure promote yield when both fertilizers are combined in the field. Addition of lime to the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizer will help to ameliorate any acidic condition that may emerge in the soil, especially if the parent material of the soil is an acid forming parent materials, which receives heavy rainfall annually, thus causing leaching of the basic cations.

Combination of these materials will guarantee continuous supply of nutrients to the crops; this according to Ewulo *et al*; (2009) and Ojeniyi *et al*; (2009) will ensure balanced nutrient supply, control of acidity, extended residual effect and improve soil physical conditions.

Materials that give lasting residual effect on the soil will not only be beneficial to the soil but will also yield economic turnover to the farmer because he may not need to keep on applying amendments each time he wants to cultivate the soil. How long the residual effects of the combination of the organic and inorganic materials added to the acidic soils will last is not quite known, it is therefore against this backdrop that the quest to research into the present work emanated. The objective of the work was to ascertain the effect of the residual application of integrated nutrient management on the growth and yield of amaranthus.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The field experiment was conducted at the research farm of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State (05°29`N and 07° 33`E). The climate of Umudike is essentially humid rainforest with a mean rainfall of 2200mm per annual, distributed over eight months (March-November). The relative humidity varies from 51% to 87% while the monthly minimum air temperature ranged from 20°C to 24°C and the monthly maximum temperature ranged from 28°C to 35°C (NRCRI, 2011). The soil of the experimental site has a sandy loam texture. The treatment for the research comprised of Sole Urea (UA) applied at 6.25t/ha, Sole CaCO₃ (LM) applied at 4t/ha, Sole pig waste (PW) applied at 10t/ha, combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea+5t/ha of mulch (PW+UA+ML), combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea+5t/ha of mulch + 2t/ha of CaCO₃ (PW+UA+ML+LM), combination of 5t/ha of pig waste + 3.125t/ha of urea + 5t/ha + CaCO₃ (PW+UA+LM) and a control (CN). The equivalent kilograms of the treatments in ton per hectare were applied to the soil. The test plant was amaranthus (*amaranthus cruentus* L) sourced from the farm center of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. The field was cleared, ploughed, harrowed and the beds were made manually. A total land area of 20m by 14m (280 m²) was marked out for the field trials with each plot measured 3.2m m by 2 m. The experiments were laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and the treatments were replicated three times. The seeds of amaranthus (*amaranthus*

cruentus L) were raised first in the nursery and later transplanted to the field at a spacing of 40cm by 40cm to give a total of 28 stands per plots. The treatments were applied once in August 2010 and after the harvest of the vegetable, the subsequent planting was done on that same piece of land in August 2011 without fresh treatment application. The following plant parameters were measured: plant height at 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 weeks after planting (WAP), dry matter yield and nutrient concentration. The data collected were subjected to the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for RCBD using the GENSTAT package while the treatment means were separated using the Fisher's least significant difference (FLSD) at 5% probability level. Linear correlations for various variables were carried out using the GENSTAT package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Amaranthus plant height measured over weeks after planting as affected by the applied treatments during the first season are presented on Fig 1. The treatments applied showed no statistical significant difference at the fourth week after planting. At the sixth week after planting PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the plant height of amaranthus over the other treatments. The same result was obtained at the eight weeks. The application of PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the plant height at the tenth week, the percentage increase of the PW+UA+ML+LM over the other treatments were as follows: 64.32% over the control, 84.22% over LM, 88.49% over PW, 88.43% over UA, 81.09% over PW+UA+ML and 91.30% over PW+UA+LM.

At the second season of planting at the fourth weeks after planting (Fig 2), PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the amaranthus height in relation to the other applied treatments. A significant increase was observed at the eight weeks of planting where PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the plant height with a value of 26.10 cm as compared to the control which had the lowest value of 14.80cm. At the tenth week of planting, the applied PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the plant height followed by PW+UA+LM.

The application of PW+UA+ML+LM at the weeks of recording of the plant heights in the first season could be attributed to the quick release of Urea and its readily availability. According to Uphoff (2002), nutrients are readily released from inorganic fertilizers than their organic counterparts and most annual crops which are heavy feeders are able to assimilate the easily released nutrients for their growth and development. As stated in the result, the same treatment (PW+UA+ML+LM) increased plant height during the second planting; the

reason for this may be due to the presence of poultry manure and mulching material which are of organic source. Organic manure have been reported to have lasting effect on the soil because of its ability to release nutrients slowly due to further decomposition and

mineralization which has a longer positive influence on soil nutritive enhancement (Ipinmoroti and Akanbi, 2012). These when taken up by plants are translated to plant growth and growth related processes.

The treatment effect on the dry matter yield of amaranthus is shown on Fig 3 and the result obtained showed that the application of PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the dry matter yield in the first season although it was statistically at par with UA and PW+UA+LM. At the end of the second season of planting, it was also observed that the application of PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the dry matter yield where as it was also statistically at par with PW+UA+LM. The increase of the dry matter yield by the application of

PW+UA+ML+LM followed by the application of PW+UA+LM could be attributed to the presence of lime which when added to an acidic soil neutralizes the acidity by precipitating the phyto-toxic exchangeable and soluble Al as hydroxyl-Al polymers (Dee *et al*; 2003). When the forms of aluminum which causes injuries to the roots of crops are precipitated, then the roots will be able to assimilate nutrients which are translated into growth and thus positively increase the dry matter yield.

The influence of the treatment on some nutrient concentration in the plant at the end of the first season of application is shown on Table 1. Plots amended with PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the nitrogen concentration while plots that received LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the concentration of phosphorus in the plants. Potassium concentration was

significantly ($P<0.05$) increased by plots that received PW+UA+ML+LM, the percentage increases of PW+UA+ML+LM in relation to potassium over the other treatments were 21.34% for the control, 47.14% for the sole lime, 39.29% for sole poultry manure, 43.57% for urea, 46.43% for PW+UA+ML and 65% for PW+UA+LM.

Table 1: Effect of treatment on leaf nutrient concentration of amaranthus (*Amaranthus cruentus* L) at the end of the first harvest

Treatment	Nitrogen (%)	Phosphorus (%)	Potassium (%)
C	2.00	0.60	0.30
LM	3.62	2.87	0.66
PW	3.80	0.58	0.55
UA	4.00	0.55	0.61
PW+UA+ML	3.90	0.54	0.65
PW+UA+ML+LM	4.08	0.56	1.40
PW+UA+LM	3.95	0.62	0.91
Lsd (0.05)	0.38	0.13	0.83

C= control, LM =Sole lime, PW =Pig waste, UA = Urea, PW+UA+ML = Pig waste + Urea+ Mulch, PW+UA+ML+LM = Pig waste + Urea+ Mulch + Lime, PW+UA+LM =Pig waste + Urea+ Lime

The residual treatment effect on the concentration of nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, calcium and magnesium in the plants are presented on Table 2. PW+UA+ML+LM significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the concentration of nitrogen and phosphorus over the other

treatments. The result on that same Table shows that amaranthus had more of potassium and calcium when the plots were treated with PW+UA+LM. Plots that received PW significantly ($P<0.05$) increased the concentration of magnesium over the other treatments.

Table 2: Residual effect of treatment on leaf nutrient concentration of amaranthus (*amaranthus cruentus* L) at the end of the second harvest

Treatment	Nitrogen (%)	Phosphorus (%)	Potassium (%)	Calcium (%)	Magnesium (%)
C	1.30	0.21	0.25	2.06	0.72
LM	1.09	0.55	0.48	2.11	0.67
PW	1.31	0.24	0.39	2.87	1.54
UA	1.71	0.48	0.54	1.87	0.79
PW+UA+ML	2.46	0.46	0.32	2.66	0.59
PW+UA+ML+LM	5.07	0.80	1.05	2.29	0.92
PW+UA+LM	3.47	0.64	1.47	3.30	1.08
Lsd (0.05)	0.12	0.07	0.02	0.72	0.10

C= control, LM =Sole lime, PW =Pig waste, UA = Urea, PW+UA+ML =Pig waste + Urea+ Mulch, PW+UA+ML +LM = Pig waste + Urea+ Mulch + Lime, PW+UA+LM =Pig waste + Urea+ Lime

It was observed that the level of the nutrient concentrations in the amaranthus (*amaranthus cruentus* L) were higher at the end of the first harvest than the end of the second planting season except for nitrogen which was increased by the end of the second harvest. Increase in the nutrient concentration of the amaranthus by the application of combination of poultry manure, urea, mulch and lime is a clear cut demonstration of the effectiveness of integrated nutrient management. The urea helps in the decomposition of the poultry manure (Ojeniyi and Adegboyey, 2003, Adeniyi and Ojeniyi, 2005) which will assist in the release of the immobilized nutrients. On the other hand, animal manure which is an organic matter is known to be the natural reserve of the organic nutrients (Ogbodo and Nnabude, 2012). This increases the efficiency of inorganic manure by providing the micronutrients that are not present in the organic manure (Manyong, *et al*; 2000). The presence of lime will help to ameliorate the acidity which may emerge as a result of the decomposition and mineralization reaction. When the acidity is ameliorated bacterial that help in the nutrient transformation will become more effective and efficient. Similarly, Amusan and Ojeniyi (2011) reported that combination of the soil inorganic and organic amendments on a Tropical Alfisol enhanced the nutrient concentration and uptake.

The correlation relationship between soil acidity indices and nutrient concentrations is shown on Table 3. From the result, pH correlated positively but not significantly with calcium, potassium and magnesium concentration as well as dry matter yield. It correlated positively and significantly ($P<0.01$, 0.5 and 0.01) with the concentration of nitrogen, phosphorus and plant height respectively.

Exchangeable acidity correlated negatively and highly significantly ($P<0.001$) with calcium and phosphorus concentration. It also correlated negatively but not significantly with potassium and magnesium concentration in addition to the plant height and dry matter yield.

Percentage calcium saturation positively correlated and highly significantly ($P<0.001$ and 0.05) with calcium concentration and plant height as well as dry matter yield. It also positively but not significantly correlated with nitrogen concentration and in the same vein negatively correlated with phosphorus at significant probability level of less than 0.05. Percentage calcium saturation also negatively correlated but not significantly with potassium and magnesium concentration. Percentage magnesium saturation negatively correlated but not significantly with calcium and nitrogen concentration in amaranthus.

Table 3: Correlation relationship between soil acidity indices and nutrient concentration

	%Ca	%K	%N	%Mg	%P	Plant Height	Dry Matter yield
pH	0.57 ^{ns}	0.81 ^{ns}	0.82 ^{**}	0.47 ^{ns}	0.50 [*]	0.96 ^{**}	0.40 ^{ns}
Ex. Acidity	-0.71 ^{***}	-0.22 ^{ns}	-0.24 [*]	-0.93	-0.69 ^{***}	-0.30 ^{ns}	-0.99 ^{ns}
%Ca saturation	0.41 ^{***}	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.59 ^{ns}	-0.02 ^{ns}	-0.29 [*]	0.54 [*]	0.98 [*]
%Mg saturation	-0.64 ^{ns}	0.67 ^{ns}	-0.99 ^{ns}	0.28 ^{**}	0.83 ^{ns}	0.98 ^{ns}	0.82 ^{ns}
%Acidity saturation	-0.49 ^{**}	-0.48 [*]	0.49 ^{ns}	0.80 ^{ns}	-0.25 ^{**}	-0.79 ^{ns}	-0.25 ^{ns}

*** = Significant at $P < 0.001$, ** = Significant at $P < 0.01$, * = Significant at $P < 0.05$, Ns = Not significant

There were positive correlations but not significant among percentage magnesium, potassium and phosphorus concentration as well as plant height and dry matter yield. It correlated positively and significantly ($P < 0.01$) with magnesium concentration.

Percentage acidity saturation correlated negatively and significantly ($P < 0.01$, 0.05 and 0.05) with

calcium, phosphorus and potassium concentration respectively, even though it also negatively correlated with plant height and dry matter yield, the correlation was not significant. Percentage acidity saturation positively correlated but not significantly with nitrogen and magnesium concentration.

Table 4: Correlation relationship between nutrient concentration and plant parameters

	Plant height	Dry matter yield
%Calcium	0.99 [*]	0.50 ^{ns}
% Potassium	0.41 ^{ns}	0.99 ^{**}
%Magnesium	0.95 ^{ns}	0.11 ^{ns}
%Nitrogen	0.39 ^{**}	0.81 ^{**}
%Phosphorus	0.38 ^{ns}	0.56 ^{***}

The correlation relationship between nutrient concentration and plant parameters is shown on Table 4. The result obtained showed that calcium correlated positively and significantly ($P < 0.05$) with plant height but insignificantly with dry matter yield. Potassium concentration correlated positively and significantly ($P < 0.05$) with dry matter yield and not significantly with the plant height. Magnesium concentration positively correlated but insignificantly with plant height and dry matter yield. There was a positive relationship between nitrogen concentration, plant height and dry matter yield and this relationship was also significant ($P < 0.01$). Phosphorus concentration positively associated with plant height though not significant but had a significant ($P < 0.001$) bond with dry matter yield.

The correlation relationship between some soil chemical properties, nutrient uptake and plant parameters are shown on Table 5. The result shows that available phosphorus negatively and significantly ($P < 0.05$) with calcium concentration and phosphorus concentration, but negatively and insignificantly correlated with magnesium

concentration and nitrogen concentration. Available phosphorus positively and significantly ($P < 0.5$ and 0.01) correlated with dry matter yield and plant height respectively.

Exchangeable calcium correlated positively but insignificantly with calcium concentration, potassium concentration, and dry matter yield and plant height. There was a positive correlation and significant ($P < 0.05$) relationship between exchangeable calcium and nitrogen concentration. Negative correlation and insignificant association occurred between exchangeable calcium, magnesium concentration and phosphorus concentration.

On that same Table 5, exchangeable potassium correlated positively but not significantly with calcium concentration, potassium concentration and phosphorus concentration. It negatively correlated but not significantly with magnesium concentration and nitrogen concentration. A positive and significant correlation existed among exchangeable potassium, dry matter yield and plant uptake.

Table 5: Correlation relationship between some soil chemical properties, nutrient concentration and plant parameters

	% Ca	%K	%Mg	%N	%P	Dry Matter yield	Plant Height
Av P	-0.34*	0.61 ^{ns}	-0.69 ^{ns}	-0.63 ^{ns}	-0.64*	0.65*	0.99**
Ex Ca	0.44 ^{ns}	0.53 ^{ns}	-0.76 ^{ns}	0.54*	-0.55 ^{ns}	0.55 ^{ns}	0.97 ^{ns}
Ex K	0.67 ^{ns}	0.85 ^{ns}	-0.39 ^{ns}	-0.86 ^{ns}	0.87 ^{ns}	0.86*	0.92*
Ex Mg	-0.43*	0.54 ^{ns}	0.75 ^{ns}	-0.56 ^{ns}	0.57 ^{ns}	0.67*	0.97*
Ex Na	-0.24*	-0.70 ^{ns}	-0.60 ^{ns}	-0.71 ^{ns}	-0.62*	-0.62 ^{ns}	-0.87 ^{ns}
Total Nitrogen	0.24 ^{ns}	0.70 ^{ns}	-0.60 ^{ns}	0.73 ^{ns}	0.85*	0.72**	0.35**

** = Significant at $P < 0.01$, * = Significant at $P < 0.05$, ns = Not significant

Exchangeable magnesium correlated negatively and significantly ($P < 0.05$) with calcium concentration but not significantly with nitrogen concentration. There was a positive correlation and significant difference between exchangeable magnesium and dry matter yield as well as plant height. It also correlated positively but not significantly with potassium, magnesium and phosphorus concentration respectively. Exchangeable sodium had a negative correlation which was also significant ($P < 0.05$) with calcium and phosphorus concentration. Furthermore, it had a negative correlation but not significant with potassium, magnesium, nitrogen concentration in addition to dry matter yield and plant height.

Total nitrogen had positive correlations and different levels of significances ($P < 0.05$ and 0.01) with phosphorus concentration, dry matter yield and plant height respectively. Besides these, it correlated positively but not significantly with calcium, potassium and nitrogen concentration. A negative correlation and insignificant association exist between total nitrogen and magnesium concentration.

The positive correlation that existed between pH, the nutrient concentration, plant height and dry matter yield and the negative correlations that were seen among the exchangeable acidity, plant height and dry matter yield could be as a result of the increased soil pH by the addition of the lime and organic matter. This according to Ano and Ubochi (2007) increases the soil pH and reduced the soil acidity. The increase in soil pH led to a decrease in exchangeable acidity, which gave rise to the enhancement of the activities of some micro organisms, which aid in the biochemical processes in the soil. This in turn led to more availability of the nutrients in the soil, which through the comfortable environment present in the soil enhanced their assimilations by the plants.

CONCLUSION

The study has basically showed that the sole application of soil amendment will not improve the amaranthus yield and the related yield parameters in the first and second season of planting; rather the integrated application of inorganic and organic manure will be advantageous to the

plant. The application of the combination of poultry manure, urea, mulch and lime were able to increase on the average plant growth, dry matter yield, the concentration of nitrogen and potassium in the first season. It also had a lasting residual effect on the soil during the second season of planting; this will ensure a continuous supply of nutrients to the crops which will be of an economic advantage to the farmer. Integrated application of organic and inorganic fertilizer in combination with lime and mulch becomes predictable in restoring the fertility of degraded acidic soils for optimal production of amaranthus (*Amaranthus cruentus L.*) in the southeastern Nigeria

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